

Indoor Localization with Bluetooth Low Energy Utilizing Different Ranging Methods

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Abstract—In this paper, indoor localization using the Bluetooth low energy (BLE) system is explored. The range estimation is performed using the phase-based measurements of the commercially available off-the-shelf BLE devices and employing different range estimation methods. The unknown coordinates of the BLE node are computed via the analytical multilateration method based on the estimated range information at each anchor. The localization performance of the analytical multilateration utilizing different range estimation methods is experimentally examined and compared with the maximum likelihood (ML) localization, which serves as the best benchmark for localization performance. The experimental results demonstrate that the high-precision range estimation using the phase-based measurements outperforms other range estimation approaches and gives the least absolute localization error. In particular, the mean of the absolute localization error of the high-precision method approaches that of the ML localization and is within 12 cm for the selected trajectory in the measurement setup.

Index Terms—Bluetooth Channel Sounding, Bluetooth Low Energy, IoT, Localization, Phase-based Ranging.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of the Internet of Things (IoT) has driven a significant shift in digital transformation, influencing advancements in business and technology. Modern IoT ecosystems consist of interconnected devices that communicate over wireless networks, and localization of objects plays a crucial role in many applications, including asset tracking, indoor navigation, and industrial automation. The Global Positioning System (GPS) is highly effective for outdoor localization; however, its indoor applicability is limited due to satellite signal attenuation and interference from complex building structures [1]. Recent advancements in Bluetooth low energy (BLE) have established it as a promising technology for indoor localization, offering benefits such as cost-effectiveness, ease of deployment, and energy efficiency compared to alternative wireless technologies like Wi-Fi and ultra-wideband (UWB). Thus, there is a growing interest in BLE systems to perform accurate localization for indoor settings [2]–[4].

Ranging techniques play a crucial role in localization, with received signal strength indicator (RSSI) being one of the most commonly used methods. This approach estimates distance by analyzing the attenuation of an incoming signal's power level [4], [5]. However, achieving accurate results with RSSI-based techniques requires precise modeling of the signal propagation environment. Various factors, including fluctuations in antenna

radiation patterns, changes in the tag's orientation, and multipath interference, can significantly degrade the performance of the RSSI-based ranging [5]. Another widely explored localization strategy involves time of flight measurements, such as time of arrival (TOA) and time difference of arrival (TDOA) [6], [7]. These methods estimate the distance by measuring the signal travel time between the transmitter and receiver, enabling location determination through techniques such as trilateration. However, TOA and TDOA approaches demand highly accurate synchronization between devices, which poses a challenge in energy-efficient and cost-sensitive wireless networks [7]. Additionally, localization can be achieved through fingerprinting and machine learning-based techniques [8]. Fingerprinting relies on collecting a comprehensive dataset of reference signal measurements, which is then used to predict the position of a target device. Despite its potential for high accuracy, fingerprinting requires an extensive, environment-specific dataset, making it resource-intensive to implement and maintain effectively [7].

Recently, researchers have explored phase-based ranging techniques to enhance the range estimation performance of the BLE systems [9]–[14]. These techniques determine the distance by leveraging the phase difference of arrival (PDOA) between transmitted and received signals. PDOA methods are typically categorized into three groups based on their operational approach: spatial, time, and frequency domains. Spatial domain methods rely on angle of arrival (AOA) information derived from phase differences of reflected signals at multiple receiving antennas, enabling node position estimation through triangulation [9]. However, these techniques are vulnerable to multipath fading and necessitate multiple receiving antennas for each anchor point. Time domain approaches estimate the range displacement by measuring phase differences between signals received at different time intervals and then combine the estimated displacement with the known initial position of the node for effective localization [10]. However, these methods depend on the initial known position and the mobility of the node, which may not be feasible in some practical localization scenarios. Frequency domain methods involve transmitting signals at different frequencies and determining the distance by analyzing phase differences between the signals received at these distinct frequencies [11]. Particularly, multi-carrier phase difference (MCPD) ranging methods have been proposed recently [12]–[14], which have been adopted as the

Bluetooth Channel Sounding (CS) [15]. Phase-based ranging requires small frequency separation between carriers that are used for measuring the phase, which in turn increases the maximum unambiguous range estimation. Although various ranging methods are studied in the literature, localization performance comparisons between them using commercially available off-the-shelf (COTS) Bluetooth devices have not been studied yet.

In this study, we investigate indoor localization utilizing the BLE technology. We explore different ranging techniques and compare their localization performance using the COTS BLE system. To achieve this, we analyze the phase-based range estimation using the MCPD method for the BLE in Section II. Next, we formulate the localization problem and examine two localization techniques, namely analytical multilateration positioning and maximum likelihood positioning in Section III. Then, we demonstrate the experimental results of the BLE system for indoor localization and compare the localization performance of different methods in Section IV. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. MULTI CARRIER PHASE DIFFERENCE METHOD FOR RANGE ESTIMATION

In this section, we present the multi-carrier phase difference (MCPD) method for the range estimation. This technique exploits the active reflector (AR) concept to analyze phase response across different frequency channels. MCPD is based on the so-called two-way range estimation, where the uncertainties related to time and phase offsets between the two nodes involved in the range estimation can be mitigated. Following the AR concept, two BLE nodes, referred to as the initiator and reflector, perform a handshake to identify the frequencies of the channels used for the phase measurements. First, the initiator transmits a constant tone, i.e., its local oscillator (LO) signal, at a carrier frequency f_c . This transmitted signal is delayed with the one-way propagation delay and captured by the reflector where a phase measurement is performed. Afterwards, the reflector transmits back a constant tone with its LO to the initiator on the same frequency channel. Subsequently, the initiator captures the delayed signal coming from the reflector to perform phase measurement. The phase terms at the reflector ϕ_R and initiator ϕ_I can be expressed respectively as [12]:

$$\phi_R = 2\pi f_c \left(\frac{r}{c} - \Delta_t \right) + \phi_0, \quad (1)$$

and

$$\phi_I = 2\pi f_c \left(\frac{r}{c} + \Delta_t \right) - \phi_0, \quad (2)$$

where c is the speed of light, Δ_t is the unknown time offset, ϕ_0 is the phase offset difference between the LO signals of the initiator and reflector, and r is the range between the initiator and reflector. By summing the phase measurements obtained at both the initiator (I) and the reflector (R), the

Fig. 1. Illustration of the multi-carrier phase difference concept for range estimation.

signal effectively traverses twice the distance r between the two devices. Consequently, the resulting phase is given by:

$$\phi_{2W} = \phi_R + \phi_I = 2\pi f_c \left(\frac{2r}{c} \right) = \frac{4\pi f_c r}{c}, \quad (3)$$

where the unknown time synchronization and phase offsets are canceled by using the AR principle as shown in (3). However, the phase rotates, i.e. wraps, between 0 and 2π for every integer value l , and hence there is a range ambiguity. Subsequently, the unambiguous range can be written as:

$$r = \frac{c}{2f_c} \left(\frac{\phi_{2W}}{2\pi} + l \right). \quad (4)$$

This implies that multiple range values might correspond to the same phase values, and thus the range estimation is subject to range ambiguity separated by the maximum unambiguous range, which can be given as:

$$r_{un} = \frac{c}{2f_c}. \quad (5)$$

The relationship between the maximum unambiguous range and the frequency is inversely proportional, as shown in (5). For example, the maximum unambiguous range $R_{un} = 0.06$ m for the frequency $f_c = 2.4$ GHz, while the maximum unambiguous range becomes around $R_{un} = 150$ m for the frequency $f_c = 1$ MHz. Thus, a lower frequency is required to achieve a longer unambiguous range.

The range ambiguity can be eliminated by using multiple carrier frequencies and measuring the phase difference between their phases as illustrated in Fig 1. Similar to (3), assume two resulting phases after signal exchange are captured for the frequencies f_1 and f_2 as:

$$\phi_1 = 2\pi \left(\frac{2f_1 r}{c} - l \right), \quad (6)$$

and

$$\phi_2 = 2\pi \left(\frac{2f_2 r}{c} - l \right). \quad (7)$$

Subsequently, the phase difference between two carrier frequencies:

$$\phi_2 - \phi_1 = 2\pi \left(\left(\frac{2f_2 r}{c} - l \right) - \left(\frac{2f_1 r}{c} - l \right) \right), \quad (8)$$

and the two-way range between the initiator and reflector can be found as:

$$r = \frac{c}{4\pi} \left(\frac{\phi_2 - \phi_1}{f_2 - f_1} \right) = \frac{c \Delta\phi}{4\pi \Delta f}. \quad (9)$$

Consequently, using multiple carrier frequencies allows to eliminate the number of cycles l , and thus increases the unambiguous range to $\frac{c}{2\Delta f}$. In this paper, we use $\Delta f = 1$ MHz frequency separation, corresponding to 150 m unambiguous range. It should be noted that reducing the frequency results in higher sensitivity of the phase difference to noise and hence increases the range estimation error. To deal with this problem, we use multiple tone exchange (e.g. $K = 80$ tones) for a large frequency separation between the first and last carrier frequencies to increase the sensitivity of range estimation to noise, while keeping 1 MHz frequency separation between carriers to achieve a long unambiguous range. In this way, the phase estimation is performed sequentially for all tones with 1 MHz frequency separation and then used for the range estimation.

III. LOCALIZATION TECHNIQUES

This section explores signal processing techniques for two-dimensional (2D) indoor localization by utilizing the estimated range. In order to achieve this, we suggest and analyze two methods. The first technique involves an analytical multilateration localization derived from an algebraic solution. The second technique is the maximum likelihood (ML) localization, which aims to maximize the likelihood of the BLE node's location by considering the known noise distribution of the localization setup. Both techniques identify and determine the unknown location of the node, represented as (x, y) , by leveraging the given estimated range information. In the context of the localization problem, we denote the unknown coordinates of the node as $P_t = (x_t, y_t)$ at a particular step t in the trajectory, where $t \in \{1, \dots, N_t\}$. Moreover, $P_{A_i} = (x_{A_i}, y_{A_i})$ represent the known locations of the anchors, where $i \in \{1, \dots, N_a\}$ and N_a denotes the total number of anchors. According to (9), the range r_i^t between the node at position P_t and i -th anchor position P_{A_i} , can be formulated as:

$$r_i^t = \|P_t - P_{A_i}\|_2 + n_i, \quad (10)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the L2 norm and n_i represents the noise realization at the i -th anchor. In the following subsections, we will investigate further processing steps for the two aforementioned localization methods.

A. Multilateration Localization

Multilateration localization involves determining the unknown location of a node by utilizing distance measurements from at least three anchors (commonly referred to as Trilateration) or more anchors (Multilateration) [16]. The analytical multilateration approach utilizes linear algebra to determine the unknown location of the node by employing several distance measurements, while disregarding the noise present in the measurement, i.e. n_i in (10). Subsequently, the multilateration localization problem for a specific time step t

can be formulated in a matrix notation as $\mathbf{S}\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{b}$, as indicated in [16]:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -2x_{A_1} & -2y_{A_1} \\ 1 & -2x_{A_2} & -2y_{A_2} \\ 1 & -2x_{A_3} & -2y_{A_3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & -2x_{A_i} & -2y_{A_i} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{S}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} x_t^2 + y_t^2 \\ x_t \\ y_t \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{p}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} r_1^{t2} - x_{A_1}^2 - y_{A_1}^2 \\ r_2^{t2} - x_{A_2}^2 - y_{A_2}^2 \\ r_3^{t2} - x_{A_3}^2 - y_{A_3}^2 \\ \vdots \\ r_i^{t2} - x_{A_i}^2 - y_{A_i}^2 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{b}}, \quad (11)$$

where the least mean square solution for \mathbf{p} can be calculated as:

$$\mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{S})^{-1} \mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{b}. \quad (12)$$

Then, the estimated coordinates of the node for a specific position P_t , denoted as \hat{P}_t , can be derived from (12). The solution presented in (12) is an algebraic closed-form expression, which means it has low computational complexity and can be implemented in devices with limited resources for real-time applications.

B. Maximum Likelihood Positioning

The ML localization determines the location of a node by maximizing the probability of its location, taking into account the noise distribution present in the range measurements between the node and all anchors. Typically, the noise associated with the range measurement between the node and each anchor can be represented as a Gaussian mixture model comprising N components, which is derived through the expectation maximization technique [17]. Therefore, the probability density function (pdf) representing the measurement noise between the node and the i -th anchor can be formulated as:

$$pdf(n_i) = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\alpha_j^i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_j^i{}^2}} e^{-\frac{(n_i - \mu_j^i)^2}{2\pi\sigma_j^i{}^2}}, \quad (13)$$

where j is an element of the set $\{1, \dots, N\}$ and α_j^i , μ_j^i , and σ_j^i represent the coefficient, mean, and standard deviation of the j -th Gaussian mixing component, respectively. The range between the node and i -th anchor is expressed in (10). Assuming that the measurements obtained from the node to all the anchors are statistically independent, the ML localization estimator can be shown as [10]:

$$\hat{P}_t = \arg \max_{P_t} \sum_{i=1}^{N_a} \log \left(\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\alpha_j^i}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_j^i{}^2}} e^{-\frac{(r_i^t - \|P_t - P_{A_i}\|_2 - \mu_j^i)^2}{2\pi\sigma_j^i{}^2}} \right) \quad (14)$$

where, (14) can be solved by using optimization toolboxes or conducting a grid search. Herein, it is important to note that the measurements represent the range relative to each anchor. Moreover, we employ the ML localization method as an upper benchmark for the performance of the multilateration technique, and thus we utilize the actual position for a given step t to compute \hat{P}_t . In addition, it is important to emphasize that ML localization requires knowledge of the parameters associated with the measurement noise distribution between

Fig. 2. Experiment hardware: Nordic Semiconductor nRF52833-DK.

Fig. 3. Illustration of the (a) experimental setup and (b) test area.

the node and the anchors in the environment. This implies that some offline measurements must be performed to estimate the noise parameters using (9), (10), and by applying the expectation maximization method [17]. However, the localization with analytical multilateration technique does not rely on any offline measurements, as it disregards the noise and executes the localization process in real-time.

IV. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

In this section, we demonstrate the experimental results of the BLE system for 2D indoor localization. To this end, we employ a measurement setup utilizing COTS products for their convenience and the ease of accessing their specifications. In particular, we utilize the Nordic Semiconductor’s nRF52833-Development Kits (DK) as shown in Fig. 2. These development kits have an internal antenna, a transmit power of 8 dBm, a receiver sensitivity of -95 dBm, and operate at the carrier frequency of 2.4 GHz. Moreover, these development kits can provide range information based on four different range estimation methods as follows:

Fig. 4. CDF of the location error based on multilateration method utilizing different ranging methods. BLE node at the coordinates $(x_a, y_a) = (1, 1)$ m.

- **RSSI:** Measures received signal power to estimate range using Friis equation (link loss) [5].
- **Phase Slope:** Measures the multi-carrier phase differencing for each frequency and obtains phase slope from the measurements. Then, it takes the average of phase slope to estimate range [13].
- **Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT):** Measures the received signal spectrum and takes IFFT to estimate delay in time, and then converts it to range [11].
- **High-precision:** Uses multi-carrier phase difference method and then applies super resolution algorithm such as MUSIC to provide improved range estimation against multipath [14].

The captured range values for each ranging method from the development kits at specific locations are recorded and transferred to the computer via a USB port. Subsequently, the collected digital data are processed according to the localization methods discussed in the previous sections.

For the measurements, we utilize the test area with a size of $x \times y$ as $4 \text{ m} \times 3 \text{ m}$ within the measurement room, as demonstrated in Fig. 3. In this configuration, 4 nRF52833-DK are positioned as “anchors” at the corners of the test area located at $A_1 = (0, 0)$, $A_2 = (4, 0)$, $A_3 = (0, 3)$, and $A_4 = (4, 3)$ meters. Additionally, an nRF52833-DK is used as a BLE node and moved along the specified trajectory. During the experiments, we optimize the orientation of the node and anchor antennas such that the received signal is maximized. We locate the BLE node at the coordinates $(x_a, y_a) = (1, 1)$ m as an initial step, then adjust its position by 20 cm at each step along the defined trajectory. The ground truth trajectory consists of $N_t = 16$ steps where the actual BLE node position varies in either the x or y direction, ranging between $x_a \in \{1, 1.2, \dots, 2\}$ m and $y_a \in \{1, 1.2, \dots, 2\}$ m. In Fig. 3, the ground truth trajectory is shown with white dashed lines and can be highlighted as an L-shape. Then, the distance between the node and each anchor is determined by the 4 aforementioned ranging methods provided by the development kits. Subsequently, the 2D positioning of the BLE

Fig. 5. Localization results based on multilateration and ML methods for the high-precision ranging.

node is calculated by employing the analytical multilateration positioning technique using the range data from 4 anchors for every step in the trajectory, as discussed in Section III. Each estimated localization coordinate is then compared to the actual ground truth trajectory position, allowing for the calculation of the 2D localization error at each step of the trajectory. The 2D localization error is calculated as:

$$L_{\text{err}} = \sqrt{(x_e - x_a)^2 + (y_e - y_a)^2}, \quad (15)$$

where (x_e, y_e) denotes the estimated position of the BLE node. We analyze the localization error for both localization processing techniques across $N_m = 100$ measurement samples, which represent realizations of the measurements for each step. First, we assess the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the 2D localization error at the initial position $(x_a, y_a) = (1, 1)$ m by using analytical multilateration positioning for different ranging methods, as shown in Fig. 4. It is observed that the high-precision ranging gives the best performance by providing the 2D localization error with 90% quantile (Q_{90}) of 0.17 m at this step in the trajectory, where it is 0.41 m for IFFT, 1.08 m for RSSI and 2.75 m for phase slope methods, respectively. Since the high-precision technique outperforms other ranging methods, we focus on it to show the best localization performance using analytical multilateration and maximum likelihood localization techniques for every step in the trajectory, as shown in Fig. 5. Then, we take the average of the measured samples for each step and show the localization results based on multilateration and ML methods for the high-precision method in Fig. 6. It can be seen that the averaged results form an L-shape, as expected from the ground truth trajectory, and the results match the highlighted dashes in Fig. 3.

Subsequently, we assess the CDF of the 2D localization error for the high-precision technique with both multilateration and ML methods at each step along the defined trajectory, as shown in Fig. 7. The experimental results demonstrate that the maximum value of 2D localization error for the high-precision technique using the analytical multilateration method

Fig. 6. Averaged localization results based on multilateration and ML localization for the high-precision ranging.

Fig. 7. CDF of the localization error for the high-precision ranging at each step along the defined trajectory.

varies from 0.09 m (best case) to 0.28 m (worst case) across different steps, while the error for ML positioning ranges from 0.07 m to 0.26 m as an upper performance limit. Finally, we aggregate the localization errors across all steps and present the CDF of the combined localization error in Fig. 8. Herein, Q_{90} denotes the 90% quantile, and MAE represents the mean absolute error. The results show that the high-precision with ML localization for all steps combined provides $Q_{90} = 19$ cm and MAE = 10 cm as an upper bound performance. Furthermore, the analytical multilateration positioning for all steps combined achieves the absolute localization error as $Q_{90} = 18$ cm and MAE = 12 cm for the high-precision, $Q_{90} = 50$ cm and MAE = 23 cm for the IFFT, $Q_{90} = 57$ cm and MAE = 71 cm for the RSSI, and $Q_{90} = 313$ cm and MAE = 262 cm for the phase slope, respectively. It should be noted that the analytical multilateration positioning neglects the noise estimation, and it computes the localization process in real time without requiring any offline measurement, as discussed in Section III. On the other hand, ML localization requires a proper noise estimation and hence increases the complexity compared to the analytical multilateration method.

Fig. 8. CDF of the localization error comparison for different ranging methods with all steps combined.

V. CONCLUSION

The indoor localization problem has been explored through BLE technology. The phase-based range estimation using the multi-carrier phase difference method is analyzed, and four different ranging approaches, namely high-precision, IFFT, phase slope, and RSSI, are investigated using the COTS BLE system. The BLE node's position within the trajectory is estimated by employing analytical multilateration localization based on the range information at each anchor point. Subsequently, the indoor localization effectiveness of the analytical multilateration method is experimentally examined and compared to the ML localization, which serves as an upper benchmark for localization performance. It is shown that the high-precision method outperforms other ranging techniques and provides the least localization error. In particular, the error in 2D localization with all steps during the trajectory combined is given $Q_{90} = 18$ cm and $MAE = 12$ cm for the high-precision method using the analytical multilateration localization. The results presented in this paper can serve as a benchmark for the comparison of different techniques employing the BLE technology.

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